

Gradual N-terminal truncation of tau dGAE (297–391) reveals the importance of 321–325 sequence for early steps of fibril formation

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ABSTRACT

The pathological conversion of intrinsically disordered proteins into β -sheet-rich amyloid filaments is a hallmark of numerous neurodegenerative disorders. In the case of tau protein, misfolding into aggregation-prone species can be promoted by truncation, motivating the present study. We employed an integrative approach combining established experimental techniques, including AFM and ThT fluorescence assay, with MD simulations to study amyloidogenic propensities of five tau truncation variants in the presence of aggregation inducers in vitro. The experimental observations were further validated by CD and NMR spectroscopy. Our experiments demonstrated that tau variants exhibit distinct amyloidogenic propensities. Tau variant spanning residues 321–391 (numbered according to the longest CNS tau isoform 1–441) represents the minimal E391-truncated construct capable of amyloid aggregation in vitro, whereas the shorter 326–391 variant failed to form fibrillar assemblies, even in the presence of aggregation inducers. All-atom (AA) MD simulations highlighted the importance of hairpin-like structural motifs during the early stages of aggregation, which appear to template subsequent fibril growth and are preferentially adopted by the Tau321–391 variant. In contrast, coarse-grained (CG) simulations revealed a pronounced α -helical propensity in Tau321–391, particularly at the N-terminal region. This elevated N-terminal helicity constitutes the most prominent structural distinction between the aggregation-competent and aggregation-incompetent variants. In both AA and CG MD simulations, the structural transitions of tau were driven by amyloid-nucleating sequence motifs, including the G-motif, PHF6**, and PAM4. Despite sharing these amyloidogenic regions, the Tau326–391 variant lacks the intrinsic amyloid propensity required to undergo productive self-assembly into ordered amyloid fibrils.

1. Introduction

Human microtubule-associated protein tau (the longest CNS isoform, 2N4R, consists of 441 residues) is one of the longest intrinsically disordered proteins (IDPs) that natively exhibit minimal tendency to self-assemble [1,2]. On the contrary, the formation and subsequent deposition of highly ordered tau filaments in the brain are neuropathological hallmarks of neurodegenerative diseases with tau pathology,

known as tauopathies [3]. Although our understanding of the exact mechanisms of tau amyloid aggregation remains limited, multiple triggers, including various post-translational modifications (PTMs), have been identified to play a role in tau pathogenesis [4]. Using cryo-EM, high-resolution structures of tau amyloid fibrils from different tauopathies have been determined, revealing the polymorphic nature of tau filaments exhibiting disease-specific conformations [5]. In relation to distinct fibrillar morphologies, specific spreading patterns and

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neuropathological symptoms have been reported across tauopathies, hindering the development of targeted anti-tau treatments [3]. This raises many questions about the structural changes driving a conformational switch from a random coil to disease-specific tau fold, eventually leading to a common cross- β architecture characteristic of amyloid filaments.

The short-sequence regions within the tau polypeptide chain with higher hydrophobicity and β -sheet propensity, referred to as amyloid motifs, are seen as mediators of the tau amyloid aggregation [6]. Along with environmental factors and PTMs, these amyloid-nucleating motifs contribute to the formation of different protofilament interfaces, which underpin the amyloid fibril polymorphism [7]. Interestingly, all identified amyloid-promoting regions [8,9] are localized within the microtubule-binding region (MTBR) that mediates physiological binding with microtubules and also forms the core of amyloid fibrils.

Despite significant advancements in tau-related research, the relationship between the structural elements of tau fibrils and the pathology of tau amyloid-related diseases remains elusive. Previous studies have identified three key amyloid-nucleating segments within the sequence of tau protein: PHF6* (²⁷⁵VQIINK²⁸⁰) in R2, PHF6 (³⁰⁶VQIVYK³¹¹) in R3 [8], and PAM4 (³⁵⁰VQSKIGSLDNITH³⁶²) in R4 [9] (Fig. 1A, B). These sequences are critical drivers of amyloid assembly. Additionally, machine learning approaches have uncovered two more amyloidogenic segments: ³²⁶GNIHHK³³¹ (referred to as G) and ³⁴⁴LDFKDR³⁴⁹ (referred to as L) [9] (Fig. 1B). In addition, another β -strand-forming segment, PHF6** (residues 337–342), has been shown to contribute to conformational changes that are relevant for tau aggregation [10].

Amyloid motifs are often preceded by PGGG motifs, which have a propensity to form short loops connecting two antiparallel β -strands, creating intramolecular hairpins [11,12]. Prior work suggests that such hairpin structures play a role in fibril nucleation by acting as aggregation seeds [13,14]. In our study, we consider amyloid-prone motifs that have been experimentally validated to form amyloid fibrils, including ³⁰⁶VQIVYK³¹¹ (PHF6) preceded by ³⁰¹PGGG³⁰⁴, ³²⁶GNIHHK³³¹ (G-motif) [9], ³³⁷VEVKSE³⁴² (PHF6**) [15] preceded by ³³²PGGG³³⁵, ³⁴⁴LDFKDR³⁴⁹ (L-motif) [9] and ³⁵⁰VQSKIGSLDNITH³⁶² (PAM4) [9] followed by ³⁶⁴PGGG³⁶⁷ motif.

To provide suitable in vitro models for studying the mechanism of tau pathogenesis, many efforts have been made to reproduce the

structures of tau filaments isolated from affected brains [16]. Moreover, minor changes in the preparation process can lead to the formation of completely different filament structures at the atomic level, such as the effect of heparin [17] inducing full-length tau filaments that diverge from the known tauopathy folds [16,18]. Cryo-EM structures of tau fibrils derived from patients' brains revealed a common cross- β amyloid scaffold that consistently spans R3 and R4 tau repeat regions, and part of the R' region (four-repeat tauopathies also have R2 immobilized in the fibril core and three-repeat tauopathies R1 region), surrounded by a fuzzy coat composed of the N- and C-terminal protein parts [5]. On the other hand, the cores of heparin-fibrillated 0N4R and 2N4R tau were formed by repeats R2 and R3 [17,19]. Lately, the potential of truncation to induce tau aggregation has been emphasized, enabling us to study tau aggregation under more physiologically relevant conditions without the need for aggregation enhancers. Moreover, the capability of truncated tau seeds to trigger the aggregation of tau isoforms with limited aggregation capacity has been demonstrated, suggesting a potential mechanism for spreading tau pathology in the brain, reminiscent of prion proteins [20,21]. Truncation could prevent the formation of the previously reported paperclip structure of full-length 2N4R tau and thus promote tau aggregation by exposing amyloid-prone regions within the microtubule-binding domain [22,23]. Monoclonal antibodies raised against brain extracts with tau pathology confirmed the presence of Glu391-truncated tau epitopes in early stages of Alzheimer's disease (AD) [24]. DC11 monoclonal antibody exclusively binds truncated tau, suggesting the requirement of a conformational epitope, and shows no immunoreactivity with healthy tau proteins [25]. The ability of tau to adopt DC11-reactive conformation stems from sequence-encoded structural characteristics within residues 321–391, which constitute the shortest DC11-reactive tau fragment [26].

The effect of truncation on tau aggregation has been reported in several studies, where gradual truncation from both protein ends removes the fuzzy coat, resulting in a highly ordered amyloid fibril core. This yields various aggregation-prone tau fragments, including the four repeat tau fragment K18 (244–372) [27], Tau151–391 [23,28], dGAE [29] or Tau304–380 [30] spanning R3 and R4 domains, which form the amyloid fibril core of AD up to the Tau295–313 peptide which covers parts of R2–R3 domains and contains PHF6 motif [31]. dGAE fragment is often used for in vitro aggregation of tau, due to its ability to aggregate into highly ordered PHFs on its own and replicate AD PHF and CTE (chronic traumatic encephalopathy) filament folds under specific conditions [16].

In the present study, we aimed to identify structural and sequence-specific features that facilitate the amyloid aggregation of tau protein. We have prepared four truncated forms of the dGAE fragment and compared their aggregation propensities under various aggregation-prone conditions commonly used in tau aggregation studies. The amino acid sequences of selected truncated tau variants contain amyloid-prone motifs. We demonstrate that a short fragment, Tau321–391, which lacks a part of the R3 domain with the amyloid-nucleating motif PHF6, can aggregate in vitro without the need for aggregation inducers. On the other hand, despite having the same amyloidogenic sequences, including newly identified G-motif, L-motif, and PAM4 [9], a five amino acids shorter fragment Tau326–391 failed to produce filaments even in the presence of heparin, indicating the role of initial N-terminal residues 321–325 preceding G-motif in tau aggregation. MD simulations were employed to further investigate the structural behavior of these two variants, potentially responsible for their different aggregation behaviors. MD simulations can provide high spatial and temporal resolution insights into the early stages of amyloid aggregation, starting with dimerization, a rate-limiting step that is challenging to be captured experimentally due to the intrinsic structural heterogeneity of early amyloid intermediates.

Fig. 1. Truncated tau variants with identified amyloid-prone sequences. (A) Domain structure of the longest full-length human CNS tau isoform 2N4R, which contains N-terminal inserts N1, N2, proline-rich region (PRD), microtubule-binding repeats R1–R4 and one C-terminal pseudorepeat R'. (B) Truncated tau proteins used in experiments, with highlighted local amyloid motifs. (C) Predictions of amyloid regions within the dGAE fragment with multiple predictors available. None of the predictors used (PASTA, WALTZ and TANGO) predicted amyloid propensity of the L-motif that was previously identified by the machine learning algorithm CORDAX [43]. (D) Opposite trends observed in amyloid propensity and solubility scores from AGGRESKAN [44] and Camsol Intrinsic [45,46], respectively. y-axis - normalized scores from predictors. Positive values indicate higher amyloid propensity and lower solubility, and negative values indicate higher protein solubility.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Expression and purification of truncated tau proteins

Truncated species dGAE (Tau297–391), Tau306–391, Tau316–391, Tau321–391, and Tau326–391 were expressed in *E. coli* strain BL21 (DE3) (Sigma-Aldrich) from a pET-17 expression vector and purified from bacterial lysates by a series of ion exchange and size exclusion chromatography steps as described previously [32]. Purified tau proteins were stored in PBS pH 7.4 at -80°C under an argon atmosphere to prevent disulfide formation. The concentration of purified tau proteins was determined from the absorbance measured at 205 nm using a DU 640 spectrophotometer (Beckman Coulter, USA). The purity and identity of purified tau proteins were verified by sodium dodecyl sulfate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and by mass spectrometry (MS) analysis. For MS analysis, tau protein sample was reduced with DTT to a final concentration of 10 mM and alkylated with iodoacetamide to a final concentration of 15 mM. The protein was subsequently digested overnight with trypsin at 37°C . The resulting peptides were separated using an Acquity UPLC M-Class system equipped with an Acquity UPLC HSS T3 column (1×100 mm length, $1.8 \mu\text{m}$ particle size; Waters, USA). Peptide separation was performed using a 30-min linear gradient of acetonitrile (5–40%) containing 0.1% formic acid at a flow rate of $75 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Mass spectrometric analysis was conducted on a ZenoTOF 7600 time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Sciex, USA). Data were acquired in data-dependent acquisition (DDA) mode, enabling comprehensive detection of ionized species above the detection threshold. Peak detection and subsequent data processing were performed using Peaks 13 software (Bioinformatics Solutions Inc., Canada). The result of MS analysis is shown for Tau321–391 (Supplementary Fig. S1).

2.2. Kinetics of various tau variants' fibril formation measured by ThT fluorescence assay

Tau variants at $50 \mu\text{M}$ concentration were incubated in 4 amyloid-prone conditions at 37°C up to 6 days: i) $1 \times$ PBS buffer, pH 7.4; ii) $1 \times$ PBS, pH 7.4 + $50 \mu\text{M}$ heparin; iii) $1 \times$ PBS, pH 7.4 + 10 mM DTT; iv) $1 \times$ PBS, pH 7.4 + $50 \mu\text{M}$ heparin + 10 mM DTT. $50 \mu\text{L}$ of each sample was incubated in 96-well half-volume plates (Corning 3881) in three replicates at 37°C and 700 rpm (orbital shaking) in a ClarioStar reader (BMG Labtech, Germany). Thioflavin T concentration was kept at 12.5 μM in each well. The ThT fluorescence intensities of the buffer and other additives were subtracted from the ThT data measured for samples containing tau protein. The graphs were plotted using SigmaPlot 12.0 software.

2.3. Atomic force microscopy imaging and analysis

AFM imaging was performed to analyze the morphology and structural features of fibrils formed by $50 \mu\text{M}$ tau variants at the final time points of ThT kinetics measurements under four amyloid-prone conditions: $1 \times$ PBS buffer, pH 7.4; $1 \times$ PBS buffer, pH 7.4 with $50 \mu\text{M}$ heparin; $1 \times$ PBS buffer, pH 7.4 with 10 mM DTT; and $1 \times$ PBS buffer, pH 7.4 with $50 \mu\text{M}$ heparin and 10 mM DTT. AFM images were acquired using an NTegra atomic force microscope (NT-MDT) in semi-contact mode, equipped with SNL-10 cantilevers, in air. The scan area for each image was set to $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ or $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$, with a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels. Height distributions of fibrillar structures were analyzed from at least three independent AFM images for each sample using Gwyddion software. Objects were identified and marked as grains, and statistical analysis was performed to quantify height variability. The box charts of the height distributions were generated using Origin 12.0 software for better visualization and further interpretation.

Twisted filaments of Tau321–391 in heparin+DTT conditions were analyzed with Trace_y software [33] implemented in MATLAB

(Mathworks). To select appropriate fibrils for analysis, the following criteria were applied in which single, separated fibrils with at least three repeat units and no visible breakage were used. Selected tau fibrils were traced and straightened using algorithms in Trace_y software. Then, the 3D surface envelope model for each filament was constructed, followed by the construction of cross-sectional contact-point density maps. The reference cross-sections of cryoEM-measured filaments - tau 2N4R heparin-induced jagged filaments (EMD-4565) and tau PHF (EMD-0259) were adapted from Lutter et al. [34].

2.4. Circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy

The samples of $50 \mu\text{M}$ tau variants Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 in buffer only and upon addition of $50 \mu\text{M}$ heparin were withdrawn from the aggregation assay at various time points (0, 23, 28, 30.5, 42, 51, 72 h). The samples were loaded into a 1 mm optical path length cell, and spectra were collected within the range 190–270 nm with a scanning speed of $50 \text{ nm}/\text{min}$ and 3 accumulations. CD spectra were recorded using the Jasco J-815 spectropolarimeter (Jasco Inc.). The CD spectra were smoothed in Origin Pro8.5 software using a Savitzky-Golay filter. The CD spectra were deconvoluted in the BeStSel program, which allows a detailed evaluation of the secondary structure of proteins, including β -rich structures [35].

2.5. Capillary electrophoresis

Electrophoretic experiments were performed using an Agilent 7100 CE electrophoretic analyzer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with UV detector. Separation was performed in a $56 \text{ cm} \times 75 \mu\text{m}$ ID bare fused silica capillary (MicroSolv Technology Corporation, USA). Samples were injected hydrodynamically at a pressure of 50 mbar for 10 s. The separation was performed in positive polarity mode. The applied voltage was increased from 0 kV to +20 kV at the beginning of the separation for 20 s. The separation was performed in a background electrolyte composed of 1 M acetic acid (pH 2.38). The detection was performed under standard constant wavelength set at 210 nm.

2.6. MD simulations

Two truncated peptides were selected for all-atom simulations, with sequences $^{321}\text{KCGSLGNIHHKPGGGQVEVKSEK}^{343}$ (Tau321–343) and $^{326}\text{GNIHHKPGGGQVEVKSEK}^{343}$ (Tau326–343), sharing an *N*-methylated carboxyl group at the C-terminus. All-atom simulations were carried out using the charmm36m force field with a charm-modified tip3p water model [36]. In the first step, three 500 ns-long replicas of monomeric Tau321–343 and Tau326–343 were produced starting from fully extended conformers built in Chimera by applying random initial velocities. The most representative structures of the resulting conformational ensemble were identified by a clustering analysis with the Gromos algorithm, which is based on RMSD measurements of the backbone positions sampled during simulations. Clusters were defined with a 3 Å cutoff. Central structures (corresponding to the frames with the lowest RMSD to all other structures grouped in the same cluster) of the top ten populated clusters were plotted into a free energy landscape (FEL). FEL was produced based on PCA analysis, producing a covariance matrix of the tau protein's coordinate fluctuations using gmxcovar. Then the trajectory was projected through two previously obtained eigenvectors using gmxcovanaeig to generate PC1 and PC2 (principal component 1 and 2) to capture the crucial movements of the proteins. Finally, using the gmxcovsham tool, the 2D free energy landscape was constructed by first creating histogram from PC1 and PC2 of sampled states and then performing a Boltzmann inversion of the histogram, to calculate free energy differences ($\Delta\Delta G$) between clusters and visualizing the structural transitions between clusters. Central structures from the top 10 clusters were located in the FEL, based on their corresponding PC1 and PC2 calculated

in the first step. Both RMSD and PCA analyses agreed on the highest populated conformations, which were further selected for dimerization simulations as follows: c11 + c12, c13 + c14, c15 + c16, c17 + c18 and c19 + c110. Selected pairs of conformers were placed into the simulation box spaced 30 Å between their geometric centers. Three 2 μ s-replicas were produced. Clustering analysis of dimerization simulations was performed only for extracted frames with intermolecular interactions (intermolecular distance cutoff was set to 0.5 nm, using RMSD cutoffs of 0.5 nm for all-atom dimers).

Coarse-grained simulations of full-length Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 variants were produced using the SIRAH 2.0 force field [37]. To better reproduce the intrinsically disordered behavior of tau, we employed a recent reparameterization of Sirah 2.0 by Martins et al. [38], who increased the interaction between water and protein beads up to 30% to reproduce the flexible behavior of other IDP, alpha-synuclein. Initial conformers of Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 were generated by AlphaFold2 to decrease the size of the simulation box and thus reduce computational costs. Trajectory analysis involving RMSD, Rgyr, end-to-end distances, clustering, secondary structure analysis, and contact maps generation was performed using incorporated GROMACS tools and the mdtraj package. The time percentage of dimeric species across replicas was statistically compared between Tau321–343 and Tau326–343 using a two-tailed *t*-test from the *scipy.stats* module. All simulations were carried out in GROMACS version 2023.2. The system setup was done locally, and trajectories were produced on the Devana HPC system.

2.7. Generation of CG input structures by AlphaFold2

The input protein conformations of Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 for CG simulations were modeled by AlphaFold2 (ColabFold v1.5.5) (AF2) [39]. Predictions from primary structure were carried out using default AF2 framework, conducting multiple sequence alignment by MMseqs2 without structural templates. Finally, the five highest-ranked structures were relaxed and set up for simulations of five CG tau replicas.

2.8. Secondary structural propensity calculation from NMR data

For the calculation of secondary structural propensities, we used the chemical shift values for Tau321–391 obtained from the 3D HNCACB NMR experiment, which we have deposited into the BMRB database under the entry code 53400. Isotopically labelled Tau321–391 was expressed in M9 minimal media with 2 g/L ¹³C glucose and 1 g/L ¹⁵N ammonium chloride using the Marley protocol, in which the culture initially grown in LB medium was concentrated 4-fold into the minimal medium before induction [40]. The spectrum was measured using a Bruker AVANCE NEO 950 MHz spectrometer with 0.5 mM Tau321–391 in PBS buffer with 5 mM DTT and 10% D₂O. Random coil chemical shift values were obtained from POTENCI [41].

Secondary chemical shifts were computed following the established procedure based on deviations of the measured chemical shifts CA and CB from random-coil reference values, according to Marsh et al. [42], and normalized by the maximum SPP value across the sequence. Positive deviations indicate helical propensity, while negative SSP values suggest the formation of β -sheets.

3. Results

In this study, we have experimentally assessed the amyloid-forming potential of various tau variants containing amyloid aggregation motifs (PHF6, G-motif, PHF6**, L-motif, PAM4, and LTFRENA). Sequences of these amyloidogenic motifs are shown in Fig. 1A and B, with their respective positions in the 2N4R tau sequence. Tau fragments dGAE (Tau297–391), Tau306–391, Tau316–391, Tau321–391, and Tau326–391 were tested under amyloid-prone conditions: i) 1 \times PBS buffer, pH 7.4; ii) 1 \times PBS + 50 μ M heparin; iii) 1 \times PBS + 10 mM DTT;

iv) 1 \times PBS + 50 μ M heparin + 10 mM DTT. Tau fragments dGAE and Tau306–391 contain all six mentioned amyloidogenic motifs, whereas Tau316–391, Tau321–391, and Tau326–391 contain all motifs except PHF6.

The amyloid propensity is well established to be encoded in sequence and is derived from higher hydrophobicity and β -sheet propensity, which reduce protein flexibility and solubility [43]. Therefore, amyloid aggregation predictors can reliably identify regions with a higher propensity toward amyloid aggregation based on their amyloid-specific properties. In addition to previously validated amyloid segments, PASTA, WALTZ, and TANGO predictors identified an additional aggregation hotspot ³⁷⁶LTFRENA³⁸² from the C-terminus of tau variants (Fig. 1B). Camsol Intrinsic and Aggrescan values (Fig. 1D) exhibit opposite trends, reflecting different physicochemical properties, such as solubility and aggregation propensity. Final scores from Camsol Intrinsic [45] (<https://www.cohsoftware.ch.cam.ac.uk/index.php/camsoltrinsic>) and AGGRESKAN [44] (<http://bioinf.uab.es/aggrescan/>) indicate one of the highest solubility and the lowest amyloid propensity of shorter protein variants Tau316–391, Tau321–391 and Tau326–391. On the other hand, Tau306–391 and dGAE containing an additional hydrophobic segment PHF6 are the least soluble and the most amyloid-prone among the studied variants (Supplementary Table S1).

3.1. Exploring the amyloid aggregation potential of tau variants

The amyloid aggregation propensity of tau protein fragments at 50 μ M concentration was investigated under four amyloid-prone conditions using a Thioflavin T (ThT) fluorescence assay (Fig. 2). DTT and heparin served as reducing agent and amyloid aggregation inducer, respectively, either independently or in combination, at final concentrations of 10 mM and 50 μ M. The results from these conditions were compared with those obtained in 1 \times PBS buffer (pH 7.4). Non-normalized ThT kinetics curves are shown as Supplementary Fig. S3.

Under phosphate buffer conditions, all tau fragments exhibited minimal fibril formation, as indicated by low ThT fluorescence intensity (Fig. 2A–F, black squares and bars).

Heparin, which interacts with positively charged regions of tau and mimics intracellular polyanions such as RNA, can induce conformational changes that promote tau aggregation [47]. The addition of 50 μ M heparin (Fig. 2A–E, red circles) induced the fibril formation in all fragments except Tau326–391 (Fig. 2E). The aggregation propensity varied among all tau fragments. Fragments dGAE and Tau306–391 had a very short lag phase under 30 min. On the other hand, the lag phase of Tau316–391 and Tau321–391 fibril formation was up to 1 day of incubation. The steady-state ThT fluorescence intensities (Fig. 2F, red bars) also differed, indicating the varying amounts and morphology of fibrils formed in the mixtures, with dGAE exhibiting the highest ThT fluorescence values.

DTT is commonly used as a reducing agent to break disulfide bonds in proteins. Reducing cysteine, in our case Cys322 in these truncated tau proteins, may lead to a reduction of intermolecular disulfide-linked dimer, which increases the propensity of tau to aggregate into amyloid fibrils [29]. In our study, we observed DTT's potential to induce fibril formation of some tau variants (Fig. 2, green triangles down). Our data showed that only dGAE and Tau306–391 (Fig. 2A, B) formed fibrils with different kinetic profiles, with dGAE forming fibrils faster than Tau306–391. The lag phase of dGAE was 3 days compared to the 4.6-day-long lag phase of Tau306–391. Other fragments did not form ThT detectable fibrils in the presence of DTT.

The combination of heparin and DTT could resemble the intracellular environment during disease progression. DTT facilitates the formation of aggregation-prone tau by reducing disulfide bonds, while heparin accelerates the aggregation process by stabilizing fibril-prone conformations. These conditions (Fig. 2A–E, blue triangles up) caused significant fibril formation in all tau fragments except Tau326–391. The kinetics of fibril formation were comparable to heparin-induced fibril

Fig. 2. The aggregation propensity of the tau fragments. Kinetics of fibril formation for various tau variants, dGAE (A), Tau306–391 (B), Tau316–391 (C), Tau321–391 (D), Tau326–391 (E), measured by ThT fluorescence assay. Tau variants at 50 μ M concentration were incubated in 4 amyloid-prone conditions up to 6 days: i) 1 \times PBS buffer, pH 7.4, 37 $^{\circ}$ C (black); ii) 1 \times PBS, pH 7.4 + 50 μ M heparin (red); iii) 1 \times PBS, pH 7.4 + 10 mM DTT (green); iv) 1 \times PBS, pH 7.4 + 50 μ M heparin + 10 mM DTT (blue). The graphs show normalized ThT fluorescence intensity values. Each kinetic curve was normalized to the minimal and maximal ThT intensities. (F) End-state ThT fluorescence values of the kinetic curves are presented as average values with SD.

formation, but with higher fibril yields except for dGAE, where the ThT fluorescence yields are comparable within experimental error (Fig. 2F). Only heparin+DTT-induced Tau316–391 showed faster kinetics compared to heparin-only induced Tau316–391 (Fig. 2C). Interestingly, the highest steady-state values were observed for Tau306–391, Tau316–391, and Tau321–391 fragments (Fig. 2F, blue bars). For dGAE and Tau306–391 fragments, kinetics was slightly slower compared to the heparin-only conditions.

3.2. Morphological variability of filaments formed by tau fragments

To confirm fibril formation and further elucidate the structural variability of fibrils formed by tau variants under amyloid-prone conditions, we employed atomic force microscopy (AFM). AFM imaging provided insights into the morphology of tau fibrils formed at the endpoint of Thioflavin T (ThT) kinetics (Fig. 3A). The measured height distributions of fibrils (Fig. 3B) revealed differences among the variants and experimental conditions.

dGAE and Tau306–391 variants formed fibrils under most experimental conditions. dGAE exhibited dense abundant fibrillar structures of varying lengths under heparin and heparin+DTT conditions, correlating with its high ThT fluorescence intensity and short lag phase. Specifically, under heparin+DTT conditions, dGAE formed long, intertwining fibrils, whereas under DTT-only and heparin-only conditions, it formed shorter fibrils. The height distribution of dGAE fibrils showed a broad range of heights up to 40 nm, suggesting heterogeneity in fibril thickness, which aligns with its dense network-like morphology. Tau306–391 formed less dense but longer fibrils than dGAE, upon the addition of heparin, DTT, or their combination. Interestingly, Tau306–391 showed lower ThT fluorescence intensity than dGAE except under DTT-only conditions. The height distribution of Tau306–391 fibrils was narrower up to 20 nm, indicating a more uniform fibril structure.

Tau316–391 formed fibrils under heparin and heparin+DTT

conditions. In the presence of heparin alone, the fibrils were less abundant and shorter compared to Tau306–391. Under heparin+DTT conditions, Tau316–391 formed longer fibrils with increased structural complexity, where some fibrils exhibited twisted morphology, which can be attributed to its slower aggregation kinetics than Tau306–391 and dGAE. The height distribution of Tau316–391 fibrils under heparin+DTT conditions revealed a greater spread, indicating variations in fibril thickness and possible bundling effects.

Tau321–391 exhibited the highest aggregation robustness, forming fibrillar structures across all experimental conditions. However, this observation contrasts with the ThT fluorescence data, where Tau321–391 demonstrated fibril formation only in the presence of heparin and heparin+DTT. AFM images revealed mostly long, unbranched fibrils with relatively homogeneous height distributions up to 10 nm, indicative of well-formed aggregates. Under heparin+DTT conditions, Tau321–391, like Tau316–391, formed twisted fibrils. The fibrils' height distribution showed minimal variation, reflecting their structural uniformity despite the twisting observed in heparin+DTT conditions.

In contrast, Tau326–391 did not exhibit any fibrillar structures under any experimental condition, which is consistent with its minimal ThT fluorescence signal. The lack of fibril formation supports the hypothesis that the truncated sequence lacks sufficient amyloidogenic propensity despite containing amyloidogenic motifs. AFM height analyses further confirmed the absence of any fibril-like structures, showing height distributions below 5 nm. However, some oligomerization of this tau form can be observed by capillary electrophoresis analysis of samples collected at different time points during the shaken incubation (Supplementary Fig. S2), but we were not able to quantify the mass of the resulting oligomer.

All morphological features of fibrils from AFM imaging are summarized in a heat map in Fig. 3C.

AFM analysis further revealed that several samples, particularly

Fig. 3. Morphological analysis of Tau variant fibril formation. (A) AFM images of tau variants at final time points of incubation (Thioflavin T assay) in all studied amyloid-prone conditions. The image size is 5×5 or $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$, with a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels. The images were obtained using an NTegra atomic force microscope (NT-MDT) with SNL-10 cantilevers. Scale bars correspond to $2 \mu\text{m}$. (B) Height distributions of tau variant after incubation in amyloid-prone conditions determined from AFM images. (C) Heat map representing a propensity of tau variants to form fibrils on scale grey-red (where grey indicates no fibril formation, light orange = $\leq 10\%$ ThT fluorescence yields, light red 10–50% ThT fluorescence yields and dark red $>50\%$ ThT fluorescence yields) and fibril characteristics (N = no fibrils, S = straight fibrils, M = mixed, polymorphic sample with straight and twisted fibrils).

Tau321–391 under PBS and DTT-only conditions, and Tau316–391 under heparin and heparin+DTT conditions, displayed highly heterogeneous distributions on the mica surface. In these cases, fibrils were present but very sparsely distributed, with fibrils separated by large fibril-free regions. Such heterogeneity implies that only a fraction of the total protein population converts into fibrillar species. Consequently, even when fibrils are clearly visible by AFM, their overall contribution to bulk ThT fluorescence may remain low. Moreover, the AFM images shown in Fig. 3 are intended to highlight representative morphologies and structural diversity rather than provide a quantitative assessment of fibril abundance.

For the twisted filaments formed by Tau321–391 in the presence of heparin and DTT we have derived the filament cross-sections (contact point cloud density maps) using the trace_y software from the AFM images. We have observed both wide and narrow filaments. The filaments seem to resemble more the dGAE PHF fold than the fold of full-length tau assembled *in vitro* in the presence of heparin (Supplementary Fig. S4).

The differences observed between ThT fluorescence and AFM imaging in our dataset likely reflect well-established limitations of ThT as a quantitative reporter of fibril load. While ThT kinetics is widely used to monitor amyloid formation, its fluorescence signal may not directly report fibril mass alone. Instead, ThT fluorescence depends on multiple factors, including fibril morphology, polymorphic structure [48], binding site accessibility [49], and surface charge properties [50]. ThT binds to repetitive cross- β structural motifs, but its affinity and quantum yield can vary substantially depending on fibril architecture and the accessibility of binding grooves [49]. Structural polymorphs, as shown for dGAE under heparin-only and heparin+DTT conditions (Fig. 2A and Fig. 3A), may therefore produce comparable fluorescence intensities despite different fibrillar mass. On the other hand, markedly different fluorescence intensities for dGAE under heparin- and DTT-only conditions may arise despite comparable fibrillar morphology. In addition, surface charge represents an additional contributing factor. As a positively charged molecule, ThT binding is influenced by electrostatic interactions. Variations in buffer composition and cofactor presence

(heparin or DTT) can alter fibril surface properties and zeta potential, thereby modulating ThT affinity independently of fibril quantity [50]. Therefore, ThT fluorescence assay and AFM imaging together provide complementary, though not always directly correlated information

about protein aggregation.

Fig. 4. The analysis of N-terminal tau fragments Tau321–343 and Tau326–343 from dimerization simulations. (A, D) Inter-monomer distance analysis of five 2 μ s replicas. Shaded area on plot D shows the contribution of N-terminal residues 321–326 to the formation of dimers. (B, E) Representative structures of the ten most populated clusters from RMSD clustering. The blue beads represent the N-terminus of the protein. Cluster percentages refer to extracted frames with intermolecular contacts (29.98% of frames for Tau321–343 and 14.98% of frames for Tau326–343). Elements of secondary structure are shown with cartoon representation as yellow arrows (β -sheet), pink helix (α -helix) and blue helix (3_{10} helix). (C, F) Contact maps depicting the frequency of intermolecular interactions between tau residues. Contact maps were generated from extracted trajectory frames with observed inter-monomer interaction, using the same criteria as in the clustering analysis. Intermonomeric distance cutoff was set to 0.5 nm in all cases.

3.3. MD simulations

Experimental data identified Tau326–391 as the only amyloid aggregation incompetent form among the studied variants. It was intriguing that only the five-amino-acid-longer variant Tau321–391 formed fibrils across several tested conditions, despite having the same amyloidogenic sequences as Tau326–391. Hence, to uncover the structural mechanisms underlying differences in the aggregation propensity on the molecular level, we utilized MD simulations of tau monomers and subsequently simulated dimerization to identify the first intermolecular contacts mediating tau self-assembly. The aim was to study, at atomic resolution, the structural changes that initiate the early steps of amyloid formation in Tau321–391 and, on the other hand, prevent the amyloid conversion of Tau326–391.

3.3.1. Residues 321 to 325 exert higher aggregation propensities to Lys343-truncated tau variants

All-atom (AA) simulations were focused on the N-terminal regions of tau, using fragments 321–343 and 326–343. These sequences share the amyloid motifs G and PHF6**, differing in their first five amino acids ³²¹KCGSL³²⁵. Given the lack of structural information for these truncated peptides, we performed unbiased molecular dynamics simulations to generate conformational ensembles. Simulations were run for 0.5 μ s in triplicate, starting from fully extended conformations. We analyzed the secondary structure content throughout simulations and observed that both fragments shared high contents of coiled conformations, with low proportions of intramolecular β structures, mainly in the form of β -bridges. Compared with the shorter fragment, Tau321–343 adopted a larger proportion of helical conformations at its C-terminal region (Supplementary Fig. S5).

Both tau fragments exhibited flexible dynamics, with fluctuating properties such as end-to-end distances, RMSD, and radius of gyration (Supplementary Fig. S6). To identify the most representative structures from the trajectories, we combined RMSD clustering with principal component analysis (PCA) (Supplementary Figs. S7, S8). Analyzing the top 10 most populated clusters, we confirmed the differences observed in secondary structure contents, with Tau321–343 adopting helical structures on its C-terminal region (clusters 1, 3, 4, and 9) and β -hairpins formed within ³²⁶GNIHHR³³¹ (G-motif) and ³³⁷VEVKSE³⁴² (PHF6**) motifs connected by ³³²PGGG³³⁵ (clusters 3, 5, and 6). In the case of Tau326–343, the most populated clusters were characterized as less compact and, except for cluster 7, contained mostly random coiled conformations (Supplementary Figs. S5, S7, and S8).

Next, to evaluate how the sequence differences between fragments and their adopted conformations determine their aggregation capacities, we simulated the dimerization process, using two copies of each peptide in solution. Selected paired conformations corresponded to the top 10 most populated clusters ($cl_1 + cl_2, cl_3 + cl_4, \dots, cl_9 + cl_{10}$). Despite the fact that no truncated tau-343 fragment formed stable dimers through the five 2 μ s trajectories, we observed multiple association-dissociation events within each simulated replica. A contact analysis was performed to determine the percentage of frames in which intermolecular contacts stabilized tau fragments. Interestingly, Tau321–343 showed a significantly higher dimeric population through the 10 μ s concatenated trajectories, with 29.4% \pm 4.4, compared with a 14.7% \pm 2.1 dimer population for the shorter fragment Tau326–343 ($P = 0.014$) (Fig. 4 A, D).

Clustering analysis revealed distinct self-assembly modes of Tau321–343 and Tau326–343 monomers during dimerization simulations. Tau321–343 clusters were characterized by higher β -contents, with intramolecular antiparallel β -hairpins that acted as dimerization surfaces, forming both parallel and antiparallel intermolecular β -sheets (Fig. 4E). Hairpin structures, as observed in our simulations, are considered highly effective aggregation seeds, capable of nucleating and spreading amyloid aggregation by forming a stable templating β -core [12,13]. On the other hand, the hairpin population of the dimeric

Tau326–343 top 10 clusters accounted for only 0.56% of the conformers and was present only in cluster 10. In contrast, Tau321–343 conformers exhibited increased β -sheet content, with hairpins observed in clusters 3 (1.2%), 4 (1.1%), and 8 (0.58%); and both parallel and antiparallel intermolecular β -structures in clusters 1 (2.2%), 6 (0.87%), 7 (0.75%), and 8 (0.58%). These observations align with evidence that early amyloid intermediates are enriched in intramolecular antiparallel β -structures, which later rearrange into parallel, highly ordered cross- β sheets characteristic of mature tau filaments [51]. Tau321–343 dimers from cluster 3 adopt a compact structure, embedding two hairpin monomers that resemble a potential early aggregation seed. On the other hand, Tau326–343 preferentially engages in fuzzy interactions, with some clusters (2, 7, 8) forming short parallel β -sheet interfaces.

The N-terminal residues 321–326 are critical for Tau321–343 self-assembly, as can be observed from the contact probability map (Fig. 4F) and β -sheet formation within G-motif residues. However, Tau326–343 dimers interact strictly via the C-terminal PHF6** motifs, with N-termini projecting away from the binding interface. Intermonomer contact analysis confirmed that Tau321–343 dimers are stabilized by C-terminal PHF6** and N-terminal G-motif interactions, while Tau326–343 dimers are stabilized solely by PHF6** motifs (Fig. 4C). Amyloid fibril formation and propensity for β -sheet formation have been experimentally demonstrated for both of these motifs [9,10].

3.3.2. Tau321–391 populates helical intermediates

In an attempt to identify structural differences between longer tau fragments studied in our biophysical assays, we performed monomeric simulations of Tau321–391 and Tau326–391. Solvent explicit simulations of 70-residue peptides would require simulation boxes containing \sim 1.7 million particles. To cope with the high associated computational costs, we selected the coarse-grained (CG) SIRAH force field, which has been previously validated for IDPs [52] and specifically tested with tau fragments [53]. CG models reduce the number of particles by grouping a set of atoms into a larger bead that reproduces the physicochemical properties of side chain functional groups. Additionally, the starting conformations of the Gly391-truncated Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 variants were not set to fully extended conformations, given the extremely large simulation boxes required. Instead, initial configurations were generated with AlphaFold2 (Supplementary Fig. S9). AlphaFold2 introduced some secondary structure elements into tau conformers, including one α -helix formed within the PAM4 motif and one C-terminal α -helix formed within the ³⁷⁶LTFRENAK³⁸³ sequence. The partial global folding reduced the protein's radius of gyration, thereby reducing the required size of the simulation box and ultimately the computational cost of the simulations.

Trajectory analysis of Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 showed how both fragments reproduced an IDP behavior, with high structural flexibility (Supplementary Figs. S10 and S11), as observed from the fluctuating end-to-end and radius of gyration measurements (Supplementary Fig. S12). Secondary structure (SS) contents for tau conformers from coarse-grained simulations were assigned using the SIRAH tools, classifying residues into helical, β -sheet, and coil configurations. MD simulations successfully replicated sequence-specific β -sheet propensities, in agreement with computationally predicted and experimentally validated amyloid-nucleating motifs, including G-motif, PHF6**, and PAM4 (Fig. 5A, B). Helical and β -sheet propensity within G-motif and PAM4 were confirmed by NMR (Fig. 5C), with one additional region preceding the ³⁷⁶LTFRENAK³⁸³ sequence with amyloidogenic propensity, as suggested from MD simulations and amyloid predictors TANGO and PASTA.

The most significant difference was in the N-terminal protein regions, as two out of five replicas of Tau321–391 adopted an N-terminal α -helix that encompassed G-motif residues (Supplementary Fig. S13). The validity of our MD results is further supported by the fact that chemical shifts calculated from the 10 most populated clusters from Tau321–391 simulation using SPARTA+ [54] correlated with the experimentally measured chemical shifts (Supplementary Fig. S14).

Fig. 5. Secondary structure propensities (SSP) of Glu-391 variants from CG and AA MD simulations, amyloid predictors, and NMR. (A) Per residue structural propensity analysis of Tau321-391 and Tau326-391 variants from monomeric MD simulations. Each replica's data point is plotted for helical (H, magenta) and β -sheet (E, golden) propensity (five 5 μ s replicas), the shaded region represents the standard deviation of H and E, and the line corresponds to the mean value. (B) Sequences with SS propensity calculated from MD simulations and three amyloid-sequence predictors with highlighted amyloid-promoting regions identified with background arrows. (C) SSP plot obtained from secondary chemical shifts, calculated from obtained $C\alpha$ and $C\beta$ chemical shifts of double-labelled ^{13}C , ^{15}N Tau321-391, and compared with reference random coil chemical shifts. Upwards-pointing arrows represent the amyloid-promoting regions as in B. The coloring scheme of secondary structure elements is the same for all panels (H- α -helix - pink, E- β -sheet (extended) golden).

Antiparallel β -sheet intermediates were observed within the conformational ensembles of both variants. These conformers comprise 7.49% of Tau321-391 structures (and represent structures from cluster 1) and 2.52% of Tau326-391 from cluster 9 (Supplementary Figs. S10 and S11). In both variants, intramolecular β -sheets were formed between the C-terminal ³⁷⁶LTFRENAK³⁸³ and N-terminal G-motif residues, while the PAM4 region shows a strong helical propensity.

3.4. Experimental-computational correlation of tau secondary structure during fibril formation

Circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy was used to characterize the conformational transitions of the Tau321-391 and Tau326-391 variants during amyloid fibril formation in two aggregation assay conditions. The CD spectra of Tau321-391 and Tau326-391 in the assay buffer and in the presence of heparin were recorded over a 72 h incubation period (Supplementary Fig. S15). Deconvolution of the CD spectra provided

estimates of secondary structure content throughout the aggregation process, allowing a quantitative assessment of α -helical, β -sheet, turn, and disordered content at defined kinetic time points (Table 1). The obtained data showed that both variants under assay buffer (heparin-free) conditions remained predominantly disordered throughout the kinetics, with more than 50% of the structure disordered and 15–20% of turns. In heparin-free samples, the antiparallel β -sheet fraction remained relatively stable over time (20.1–23.6% for Tau321–391 and 23.1–34.1% for Tau326–391), suggesting no formation of ordered β -sheet assemblies. Interestingly, the Tau321–391 variant showed a detectable increase in helical content during the lag phase at 23 h and 28 h of the incubation period, with 0.6% and 5%, respectively. In contrast, Tau326–391 showed a very limited increase in helical content, up to 0.1%, at 42 h.

The presence of heparin induced more pronounced structural reorganization in the case of Tau321–391. During the lag phase, an increase in helical content was observed at 28 h of Tau321–391 aggregation, similarly to that observed under heparin-free conditions, but to a lesser extent. Tau321–391 acquired detectable helical and parallel β -sheet contributions at later time points, accompanied by reduction in the other/disordered and turns fractions, confirming formation of ordered β -sheet amyloid fibrils. Tau326–391 showed a more stable distribution of all secondary structure components during incubation, with a slight shift toward increased β -sheet content.

These data were subsequently compared with MD simulations. Consistent with the computational (and NMR) data, the dominant tau population remained largely disordered during the early stages of amyloid formation. CD data for Tau321–391 indicate the presence of transient, interconverting helical and turn-enriched intermediates forming during the lag phase. Also, helical propensity was observed from the SSP calculation based on NMR chemical shifts. CD measurements also revealed a substantial proportion of tau enriched in

antiparallel β -sheet content in both constructs, potentially corresponding to the hairpin structural motifs observed in simulations. Notably, only the Tau321–391 variant underwent a subsequent elongation phase, characterized by a progressive increase in parallel β -sheet content, with a simultaneous rise in the α -helical signal. Such coordinated changes are consistent with previously proposed models in which transient helical intermediates facilitate aggregation by locally concentrating amyloid-prone motifs, thereby promoting the transition toward parallel β -sheet-rich fibrillar structures [55].

4. Discussion

For our aggregation studies, we have used experimentally robust conditions (PBS, DTT, heparin) to compare the aggregation of different truncated tau variants, and we have also employed heparin-free conditions. The use of heparin can be beneficial to obtain reproducible results with previously not studied tau variants or for future studies with small molecular inhibitors or antibodies [56,57]. Heparin-induced aggregation is not intended to fully replicate fibril formation in the Alzheimer's disease brain. It should be noted that the resulting assemblies are likely to differ from those formed *in vivo*, where tau aggregation is influenced by multiple factors, including various truncation patterns, post-translational modifications, and the cellular environment. Heparin is widely used to promote tau aggregation *in vitro*; however, this process may bias the aggregation pathway and the structural features of the resulting fibrils. Therefore, the data presented here should be interpreted in the context of a simplified and controlled model system, providing insights into the sequence determinants of tau fibrillization. Our kinetics data revealed distinct patterns among the variants (Fig. 2). dGAE and Tau306–391 exhibited similar aggregation behaviors under the studied conditions, forming amyloid fibrils efficiently in the presence of inducers, most likely as they contain all of the identified

Table 1

Secondary structure content determined by deconvolution of CD spectra measured at various time points during the kinetics of fibril formation of Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 variants in $1 \times$ PBS buffer or in the presence of $50 \mu\text{M}$ heparin.

Secondary structure	0 min	23 h	28 h	30.5 h	42 h	51 h	72 h
Tau321–391							
Helix	0	0.6	5	0	0	0	0
Antiparallel sheet	23.6	20.2	21.9	24.2	24.7	25.4	20.1
Parallel sheet	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turn	15.3	17.7	15.8	14.9	19	16.9	19.4
Others	61	61.5	57.2	60.9	56.3	57.7	60.5
RMSD ^a	0.3054	0.2827	0.4187	0.4064	0.336	0.2146	0.2237
Tau326–391							
Helix	0	0	0	0	0.1	0	0
Antiparallel sheet	27.1	26.7	30	23.1	31.3	27.9	34.1
Parallel sheet	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turn	18	18.9	18.5	19	19.1	18.7	17.9
Others	54.9	54.4	51.5	58	49.5	53.5	48
RMSD ^a	0.2364	0.2054	0.1707	0.2381	0.3873	0.2226	0.25
Tau321–391 + heparin							
Helix	0	0	1.1	0	0	4.3	6.7
Antiparallel sheet	25.7	19.9	20.8	22.4	32.2	31.3	31.4
Parallel sheet	0	0	0	0	0	5.5	9.4
Turn	20.5	19.3	14.4	16.3	15.9	11.9	9.9
Others	53.8	60.8	63.7	61.3	51.9	47	42.5
RMSD ^a	0.1923	0.3197	0.2837	0.4176	0.199	0.0833	0.1783
Tau326–391 + heparin							
Helix	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.6
Antiparallel sheet	26	25.7	27.3	25.5	26.4	27.6	27.7
Parallel sheet	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turn	19.8	17.1	18	17.1	16.1	17.4	19.4
Others	54.2	57.2	54.7	57.4	57.6	55.1	52.3
RMSD ^a	0.3491	0.374	0.138	0.2308	0.2882	0.17	0.3789

^a RMSD is the spectral deviation of measured CD spectra and fitted spectra from BestSel software.

amyloidogenic sequences. Tau316–391 and Tau321–391 displayed fibril formation selectively, requiring the presence of heparin to exhibit ThT-positive fibril formation propensity, suggesting that the missing PHF6 sequence in these variants is slowing down the aggregation. Tau326–391 did not form fibrils under any tested condition, suggesting its truncated sequence lacks sufficient aggregation propensity even though it contains the same amyloidogenic sequences as Tau316–391 and Tau321–391. These data are in agreement with the predictions of aggregation propensity (Fig. 1C, D). dGAE, which displayed the highest predicted aggregation propensity, was also the least soluble and most aggregation-prone variant experimentally. On the other hand, Tau326–391 exhibited the lowest predicted aggregation propensity and the highest solubility, correlating with its inability to form ThT-positive fibrils. Tau306–391, Tau316–391, and Tau321–391 showed intermediate behaviors, aligning well with the results of computational predictors.

Interestingly, the presence of the reducing agent DTT also influenced aggregation. All studied fragments (except Tau326–391) contain a single cysteine residue at position 322, allowing only intermolecular disulfide bond formation. Previous studies have shown that the formation of disulfide bonds between tau molecules can significantly impact aggregation, however both inhibitory and aggregation-enhancing effects were observed. A predecessor study reported that inhibiting disulfide bond formation in tau variants with a single cysteine residue suppresses tau aggregation [58]. However, a recent study using dGAE variant showed enhanced self-assembly under reducing conditions and for C322A mutant [59]. In line with the recent results, we observed that DTT promoted fibril formation in the most aggregation-prone variants, dGAE, Tau306–391 and Tau321–391. It was also shown that the dGAE-C322A mutant forms fibrils of similar morphology to dGAE, but with slightly reduced ThS fluorescence after 48 h, indicating fewer ThT/ThS binding sites rather than a complete loss of aggregation capacity [29]. This suggests that cysteine-mediated disulfides are not essential for aggregation and that their reduction may shift the aggregation process toward alternative pathways. Disulfide formation was shown to inhibit aggregation at low concentrations of dGAE [29]. This alternative pathway is also reflected in the morphology of the resulting amyloid fibrils (Fig. 3A, C). In the presence of heparin alone, dGAE formed predominantly short, straight fibrils. However, when DTT was added together with heparin, the fibrils were markedly longer and exhibited a distinct twisted morphology. A similar effect was observed for Tau316–391 and Tau321–391, where the combination of heparin and DTT promoted the formation of longer, more mature fibrils compared to heparin alone (Fig. 3A, C). These observations support the idea that the redox state of Cys322 can modulate not only aggregation kinetics (Fig. 2, green curves), but also the structural organization of the resulting fibrils. Interestingly, our simulation results have ruled out the role of cysteine contacts in the interaction between tau monomers (Supplementary Fig. S16).

The tau constructs analyzed in this study represent truncated variants of tau dGAE fragment (306–391, 316–391, 321–391, and 326–391), which serve as a simplified model for investigating the intrinsic amyloidogenic properties. In vivo, however, tau can undergo a variety of proteolytic truncations and post-translational modifications, and the aggregation behavior of resulting fragments may depend strongly on the precise N- and C-terminal sequence. Since the studied tau variants share most of the amyloidogenic hotspots (except for PHF6), we should not rule out the influence of the N-terminal and C-terminal flanking regions on the aggregation behavior of individual amyloidogenic hotspots. Some of the potent aggregation-prone tau fragments bear positively charged amino acids near their N-terminus – sequence of dGAE starts with ²⁹⁷IKH and sequence of Tau321–391 starts with ³²¹K. The presence of these basic amino acids could influence the behavior of its neighboring amyloidogenic hotspot (PHF6 in the case of dGAE and G-motif in the case of Tau321–391). It was previously shown that the conformation of amino acids in the regions preceding the amyloidogenic hotspot can influence its aggregation properties, for example, the cis-trans

conformation of proline influenced the aggregation of a peptide containing the PHF6 [11]. Flanking regions can both inhibit and promote aggregation [60].

MD simulations revealed structural differences that may help explain the distinct aggregation propensities of Tau321–391 and Tau326–391. Clear structural differences between the two tau variants were observed in the N-terminal region in both AA and CG representations. The N-terminal amino acids ³²¹KCGSL³²⁵ strongly shaped the conformational ensemble of the Tau321–391 variant and resulted in a two-fold increase in the association rate of Tau321–391 monomers compared to Tau326–391 (which lacks this region) in the dimerization simulations (Fig. 4A, D). Specifically, sequence 321–325 enabled the formation of β -sheets as part of a three-dimensional structural hairpin motif that was frequently adopted by Tau321–391 (Fig. 4E). This hairpin conformation was observed in both monomeric (Supplementary Fig. S7) and dimeric simulations (Fig. 4E), and an association between two hairpin-containing monomers was also detected. A recent study identified a transition state in which a third hairpin monomer spontaneously converts from an antiparallel to a parallel arrangement within a trimer by forming a cross- β nucleus that templates subsequent fibril growth, and suggests that the hairpin trimer represents a minimal amyloid nucleus [61]. Therefore, further oligomerization simulations could provide additional insight into the role of this motif in higher-order assembly. Tau326–343 monomers were self-assembled through a homotypic binding interface with parallel β topology (Fig. 4B).

At the same time, the 321–325 region displayed a pronounced helical propensity in the G-motif residues, resulting in an N-terminal α -helix that was present in a large fraction of Tau321–391 conformations (Fig. 5A). Taken together, these local and global structural differences may underlie the distinct aggregation behaviors observed for the Tau321–391 and Tau326–391 variants.

Tau monomers populate a conformational ensemble dominated by disordered states with local α -helical and β -sheet elements, primarily localized within amyloid-nucleating sequences (Fig. 5B). Secondary structure propensities derived from simulations and validated by NMR secondary chemical shifts and CD spectroscopy align closely with computationally predicted and experimentally confirmed amyloidogenic regions (Fig. 5, Table 1).

5. Conclusion

Our ThT kinetic results revealed clear differences in the aggregation propensity across the studied tau variants. The dGAE fragment showed the strongest aggregation response, forming fibrils under all induction conditions tested (DTT, heparin, and heparin+DTT). In contrast, truncation of the tau sequence led to markedly slower aggregation kinetics in each condition, with the shortest construct, Tau326–391, showing no detectable aggregation. Notably, Tau321–391 was the only fragment capable of forming fibrils in pure PBS buffer; however, these fibrils did not exhibit ThT fluorescence. Morphological characterization further demonstrated that tau variants produced fibrils with diverse heights and structural features, including straight fibrils of varying lengths. Under heparin+DTT induction, several variants - dGAE, Tau316–391, and Tau321–391 - also formed twisted fibrils.

MD simulations demonstrated that even minor sequence differences can substantially modulate the overall structural propensities of tau protein variants. In the Tau321–391 construct, five N-terminal residues adopted conformations with increased amyloid propensity during the simulations. All-atom simulations of Tau321–343 fragment revealed the formation of a highly effective amyloid-seeding hairpin fold, whereas in coarse-grained simulations, initial 321–326 residues enabled formation of the N-terminal helix within G-motif, being the most prominent structural difference between the two variants. Although a hairpin fold was transiently observed in monomeric simulations of Tau326–343, it was significantly reduced in dimeric assemblies. The higher prevalence of Tau321–391 intermediates enriched in β -sheet structures compared to

Tau326–391 may indicate an increased likelihood for Tau321–391 to sample aggregation-prone conformations.

Our findings highlight that, beyond the core amyloid-forming motif PHF6, other amyloidogenic motifs and their flanking residues can critically influence the early stages of tau oligomerization and can constitute key features of preaggregation tau conformation, and therefore could also be considered as potential therapeutic targets.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Stefana Njemoga: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Petra Majerova:** Investigation. **Juraj Piestansky:** Investigation. **Zuzana Gazova:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Pavel Kaderavek:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Exequiel E. Barrera:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zuzana Bednarikova:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ondrej Cehlar:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

We have nothing to declare.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2026.152066>.

Data availability

The computational data that support the findings of this study are available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17830302> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18157196>.

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